

Inhibition of Ultrasonic Decomposition of Aqueous Organic Halides in presence of Ethanol, Acetone, and Dioxane

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The inhibition of sonochemical decomposition of aqueous solution of some organic halides by ethanol, methanol, acetone, and dioxane has been studied. All of them have been found to inhibit the reaction considerably. The inhibiting effect of these substances may be ascribed to some one property or a combination of many properties, such as vapour pressure, surface tension, viscosity, dielectric constant, internal pressure, etc.

Several organic liquids are known to inhibit the chemical reactions taking place in the field of high frequency intense sound waves. Although Virtanen and Elfolk¹, Bresler², and others studied the effect of volatile substances on sonochemical reactions, the actual mechanism of the inhibitory reactions remains controversial and requires further investigation. The effect of ethanol, methanol, acetone, and dioxane on the sonochemical decomposition of aqueous solutions of tetrachloropropane, tetrachloroethane, and trilene has been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

A saturated solution of 1,1,1,2-tetrachloropropane of L. Light and Co. Ltd., Colubroch Bucks, England (b.p. 152°, D_{20}^{20} 1.473 and solubility in water 0.102 g./100 g.) was prepared in redistilled water. A portion of this solution (20 ml) was mixed with redistilled water (5 ml) and exposed to ultrasonic waves from a Mullard's high frequency ultrasonic generator of type E-7562 with a barium titanate transducer having a frequency of 1 Mc./sec. in a 250-ml Jena bottle. The R. F. output to the crystal was kept constant about 1.7Kv throughout. As a result of ultrasonic exposure, changes in the values of specific conductance were noticed and recorded from time to time. Similarly, the changes in the conductance values were determined when the same solution was exposed with varying amounts of ethanol, methanol, and acetone separately. The values of specific conductances, thus obtained, were plotted against the time of exposure. The results are shown in Fig. 1-3.

To ascertain the manner in which dioxane inhibited the sonochemical reactions, the kinetics of sonochemical decomposition of aqueous solution of trichloroethylene in presence of different amounts of dioxane was studied. A saturated solution of trichloroethylene (D_{20}^{20} 1.4517, solubility 0.1042) with 0, 0.4, 2.0, and 4.0% dioxane was separately subjected to ultrasonic radiations for different times of exposure and the changes in specific conductances were noted. The results are shown graphically in Fig. 4.

1. *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1952, 6, 880.
2. *Physicochim., URSS.*, 1940, 12, 323,

In another set of experiments, a saturated solution (25 ml) of *sym.*-tetrachloroethane (D^{20} 1.588, solubility 0.202 at 30°) with varying amounts of ethanol was exposed to ultrasonic waves for 15 min., keeping the other conditions the same. Similarly, the same volume was irradiated for 10 min. only with varying amounts of acetone. The amount of chlorine,

Time of exposure in min.
FIG. 1. Effect of ethanol.

Time of exposure in min.
FIG. 2. Effect of methanol.

Time of exposure in min.
FIG. 3. Effect of acetone on the aq. soln. of tetrachloropropane.

liberated as a result of ultrasonic exposure, was estimated in both cases with *N*/20 silver nitrate. The results are plotted in Fig. 4.

FIG. 4. Effect of EtOH and acetone on tetrachloroethane decomposition.

FIG. 5. Effect of dioxane on the decomposition of aq. trilene soln.

DISCUSSION

The effect of some organic liquids on the sonochemical decomposition of organic halides, namely, tetrachloropropane, tetrachloroethane, and trilene, has been investigated in two different manners. In one case, the kinetics of the reactions was studied conductometrically, firstly by adding different amounts of organic liquids and secondly in absence of these liquids (Fig. 1-3 & 5). In the second case, only the sonochemical yield of halogens was measured by varying the percentage of liquids (Fig. 4). The organic liquids studied have been found to inhibit the halogen yield and the rate of reaction. In Fig. 1 and 2, curves designated by A were obtained when the solution was exposed without adding ethanol and methanol. It is clear from Fig. 1-3 and 5 that as the percentage of liquids is increased, the rate of the reaction becomes slower and in the case of acetone and dioxane, there is a sharp decrease in the reaction rate; only dioxane seems to be the best inhibiting agent (Fig. 5); acetone comes next (Fig. 3). The curves shown in Fig. 4 demonstrate that the yield of chlorine decreases as the amounts of ethanol and acetone are increased. The inhibition of acetone (exposed for 10 min.) is much more than that of ethanol (exposed for 15 min.). The inhibitory effect of these organic liquids may be explained in the following manner.

(i) Increase in the percentage of organic liquids (ethanol, methanol, acetone, and dioxane) results in a decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. It appears that an increase in dielectric constant favours the reaction (dielectric constant of water: 76.3 at 30°).

(ii) It may so happen that the halogens, liberated in the decomposition of organic halides, act on the organic liquids and produce some stable halogen compounds. Further, the ultrasonic cavitation energy would again cause their decomposition and the net result would depend on the relative stabilities of these compounds.

(iii) The inhibition of decomposition by organic liquids tried may be further due to the high vapour pressure of most of these substances, causing suppression of the cavitation.

Virtanen and Ellfolk¹ observed in the oxidation of aliphatic fatty acids, aldehydes, alcohols, and aromatic hydrocarbons that a substance of high vapour pressure, such as ether or ammonia, prevented the breakdown of the cavitation bubbles. This theory has been supported by Khenokh and Lupinskaya² and by Taki and Kunitomi⁴. In our case, internal pressure of the aqueous solutions of organic substances may be further suppressed, leading to more cavitation to inhibit the action of ultrasonic waves.

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3. *Zhur. Obsh. Khim.*, 1956, 26, 2430.

4. *J. Chem. Soc. Japan, Pure Chem. Sec.*, 1951, 72, 820.